

*Equality Diversity and Inclusion for
Research Enhancement in Bosnia Herzegovina*

EDiRE

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Deliverable abstract

The current deliverable D6.3 describes the outcomes of EDIRE's dissemination and communication (DC) strategy and action plan implementation during the second reporting period (RP2), from March 1st, 2024, to the end of the project, October 31st, 2025. Apart from detailing the DC activities, it also measures the results considering the target values or KPIs achieved in terms of dissemination and communication, and in addition, it offers a qualitative assessment of the project's global communicational outreach.

D.6.3 Dissemination and Communication package - RP2 is based on the strategic guidelines included in the previous D6.1 Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation plan, and it relies on EDIRE's overall DC policy aimed at maximizing project impact, whereas EDIRE's specific exploitation and sustainability plan is included in a separate deliverable D6.4.

The deliverable contains all the EDIRE dissemination and communication activities and products produced during the RP2, including promotional materials, snapshots of the website, references to owned social media, use of EC communication tools, media relations and coverage, external events participation and presentations, project events organization and evaluation, publications achieved, and description of liaison activities with other relevant projects.

This report is a continuation of D6.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation package - RP1.

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1. Introduction

An operative and SMART - Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic, and Timely - Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Strategy contributes to a research project's success and outreach. EDIRE's DC policy is based on careful planning, including objectives, strategies, target groups, calendars as well as, the assessment means and key performance indicators (see D6.1 for a more detailed description). The present D6.3 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Package – RP2 (M38) contains all the relevant dissemination and communication activities carried out by EDIRE consortium during the second evaluation period. It documents the actions and products achieved by the end of the project. The report also assesses the EDIRE's overall DC results in KPIs.

EDIRE's intensive DC activities have contributed to the achievement of the project's specific objectives, in an intrinsic way or indirectly: 1) SO1 Enhancing the scientific and technological capacity of SSST, contributing in raising its attractiveness, research profile and reputation, by fostering SSST and BA researchers visibility and capacities; 2) SO2 Enhancing internationalisation and networking activities, by informing about and fostering international and joined action; 3) SO3 Strengthening SSST research management capacities and administrative skills, by communicating training opportunities.

Giving continuity to the previous DC report D6.1, this current package includes: all promotional materials developed; snapshots describing main sections of the project website; references regarding social media use; EC dissemination tools employed including radio and TV broadcasting; text of all the press releases published; the press conferences organized and related press reviews; agenda of the attended events external to the project and the presentations given; agenda, presentations and participants' satisfaction questionnaire regarding the project events organized in RP1; references to all publications produced in the RP, as well as information on liaison activities.

1.1 Abbreviations/Acronyms

BA	– Bosnia and Herzegovina
BCS	– Bosnian, Croatian, Serbian
DC	– Dissemination and Communication
DCE	– Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation
DCEP	– Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan
DCP	– Dissemination and Communication Plan
EC	–European Commission
ECR	– Early Career Researchers
EDI	– Equality, Diversity, Inclusion

RP	– Reporting Period
GA	– Grant Agreement
GE	– Gender Equality
GEP	– Gender Equality Plan
GM	– Gender Mainstreaming
HE	– Higher Education
HEI	– Higher Education Institution
KoM	– Kick-off Meeting
MS	– Milestone
M	– Month
R&I	– Research and Innovation
RP	– Reporting Period
SSST	– Sarajevo School of Science and Technology
SO	– Specific Objective
TUD	– Technological University Dublin
UCM	– Universidad Complutense
UNIGE	– Università degli Studi di Genova
URCA	– Université de Reims Champagne-Ardenne
Y	– Year
WB	– Western Balkans

2. Dissemination and communication strategy key points and goals

All the project's DC actions and initiatives were based on a strategic plan (see D6.1) to ensure that activities are effective, proportionate to the action's scale, and capable of reaching audiences both within the project's community and stakeholders beyond it. Hence, EDIRE's DCP included an action plan for both internal and external stakeholders.

Internal dissemination and communication strategy

The internal dissemination strategy was aimed at enhancing networking activities between SSST and partner organizations, as well as engaging SSST management, staff, and students to increase the university's management capacities to participate in the project's core activities. Several departments (e.g. Computer Science, Medical School, Economics, Political Science) and units (academic and administrative), as well as postgraduate and advanced undergraduate students, were involved in EDIRE activities and targeted in the internal dissemination plan.

These internal activities included, among others, creating internal working groups engaging both SSST staff and external decision makers and experts, to foster gender equality, diversity, and inclusion policy and action within the academic institutions. Internal communication was performed in various formats, among others: meetings, working sessions, EDIRE website, newsletters and social media, personal communications, calls for training and other activities distributed by email and/or other project communication outlets.

External dissemination and communication strategy

EDIRE's external dissemination plan was focused on the dissemination of the project findings to the diverse national and international target groups interested in or engaged in gender, equality, and diversity-related themes. Outputs, outcomes, and other core aspects of the project were shared with expert and organisational audiences through social media, EDIRE website, conferences, journal articles, project dissemination events, newsletters, liaison activities, and other scientific dissemination methods. The project's website and promotional materials (e.g. flyers) supported many of the dissemination and communication efforts. Exploitation activities were used to encourage the adoption of strategies and plans developed within the project, as well as to distribute policy recommendations among key stakeholders. These audiences were targeted in both the short and medium term (for a detailed record of exploitation activities, see D6.4).

Diverse institutional, academic and professional groups were targeted by EDIRE dissemination activities: a) academic and non-academic organisations performing R&I activities, especially in the Western Balkans, b) professional associations, c) decision makers in universities and research centres, d) civil society and grass root organizations and enterprises, e) governmental research and equality institutions at national, European and global level and f) national and international policy makers, from

several EU countries. Also, key internal stakeholders from SSST, partner organizations, and partners' relevant contacts in the field of EDI were addressed.

EDIRE'S overall communication strategy was designed to raise deep awareness of the project in the public arena and inform about its added value, especially to the public beyond the scientific community at local, regional, national, and international levels. The aim was to share and promote project outcomes and outputs and foster their potential exploitation. Also, increasing awareness on EDI, GE and GM related policies and activities in academia were in the focus, using the experience and learnings gained in the EDIRE project. The main channels for EDIRE's communication plan included the project website and blog, social media (X, Facebook, Youtube, LinkedIn, and Instagram), press releases and media relations, Open-Science events as well as promotional materials, such as EDIRE brochures in all project languages.

Graphic 1: Differences between communication, dissemination and exploitation by EC. Source:

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf

The core target groups for EDIRE communication efforts included: a) students and early career researchers (ECR) at different levels, b) universities, c) research institutes, d) enterprises, e) policy makers and f) public (e.g. mass media and social media audiences).

A detailed description of EDIRE's dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities during the first evaluation period can be found in D6.2., whereas the project's exploitation and sustainability plan is included in D6.4.

As a guideline to distinguish between dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities, EDIRE used the above EC infographic. Nevertheless, in practice, CDE objectives and activities have important synergistic effects and overlap; the same channels can be used for multipurpose effects.

2.1 Dissemination and Communication channels and indicators

During RP2, the following channels have been used to communicate EDIRE action and results, to disseminate project results and knowledge, supporting a variety of activities that have also contributed to the exploitation of project results. The following table resumes the main channels (types of DC) as well as the assessment system, which is based on predetermined quantitative indicators and target values, e.g. key performance indicators (KPIs).

Table 1. EDIRE Dissemination and Communication KPIs.

Type	Assessment
Project website (M1-M36)	Indicator: number of hits. Target Values/KPIs: >2000 by the end of Y1, > 3600 by the end of project life. Means of verification: Reports from website facility for counting number of accesses.
Promotional material (M3)	Indicator: N. of brochures created and distributed. Target Values: >1500 by the end of Y1, > 3000 by the end of project life. Means of verification: Distribution via events and through partners' channels.
Open access scientific publications (M6-M36)	Indicator: N° of articles. Target Values: At least 5 accepted submissions at the end of the project. Means of verification: List of publications inserted in SyGMA.
Project events <i>Group 1: Project management meetings</i>	Indicator: N° of external stakeholders involved. Target Values: At least 2 external experts involved in each meeting. Means of verification: Attendance proof, presented materials, photos, event's reports.
Project events <i>Group 2: Project dissemination events</i>	Indicator: N° of participants and N° of countries represented. Target Values: > 50 external participants per event; > 10 internal participants per event Means of verification: Attendance proof, presented materials, photos, event's reports.
Project events <i>Group 3: External events</i>	Indicator: N° of events attended where EDIRE is presented and promoted. Target Values: > 10 external events during the project. Means of verification: Attendance proof, presented materials, photos, event's reports.

<p><i>Project events</i></p> <p><i>Group 4:</i></p> <p>Summer schools and seminars</p>	<p>Indicator: N° of activities, n° of participants.</p> <p>Target Values: At least 2 summer schools organized; at least 4 virtual trainings; at least 2 training per semester.</p> <p>Means of verification:</p> <p>Attendance proof, presented materials, photos, event's reports.</p>
<p>Project Newsletter (M6-M36)</p>	<p>Indicator: N° of issues and N° of addressees.</p> <p>Target Values: ≥6 issues (2/year); at least 500 addressees for each issue in Y1, with a 10% increase per year.</p> <p>Means of verification: E-Newsletter on the website and number of downloads and e-mails sent.</p>
<p>Liaison activities (M6-M36)</p>	<p>Indicator: N° of EU funded project addressed</p> <p>Target Values: at least 3 projects during the project overall duration</p> <p>Means of verification: Contents of dissemination and communication packages (D6.3 and D6.4)</p>
<p>Social media (M1-M36)</p>	<p>Indicator: N° of Likes and Shares, Tweets and Retweets with certain selected hashtags; N° of participants to initiatives (followers); N° of publications on the web</p> <p>Target Values: at least 10% increase per year, after Y1 (starting from a baseline on 500 contacts per partner) as for the N° of followers; at least 5 publications on the web blog by M36</p> <p>Means of verification: reports from such networks to be kept alive via regular posting and monitoring; blog statistics.</p>
<p>Press releases and media relations (M1-M36)</p>	<p>Indicator: N° of quotes on newspapers, television, websites; Radio and TV contributions</p> <p>Target Values: At least 15 articles in either newspaper, magazines, radio by the end of the project; at least 2 reports per year on radio or TV programs by M36.</p> <p>Means of verification: Proof of publications or videos.</p>
<p>Participation in Open- Science events (M6-M36)</p>	<p>Indicator: N° of events where EDIRE is presented and promoted.</p> <p>Target Values: >3 events attended during the project.</p> <p>Means of verification: Attendance proof, presented material, photos, events' reports.</p>

3. Activities Overview due M38

During RP2, the consortium members have performed the main dissemination and communication activities included in EDIRE's DCE Plan (see D6.1 and D6.2 for more details). Moreover, new additional communication materials and activities have been designed and carried out, summing to the former DC efforts, e.g. EDIRE rollups, smaller scale academic events in partner organizations, summer school and other event promotional materials.

3.1. Project website

EDIRE website has served and is still functioning as one of the main channels for informing and promoting project activities and outcomes and will remain updated 5 years after the project ends. Together with other dissemination and communication activities, the website has contributed to the visibility and internationalisation of SSST. It is aimed not only at experts in the field, but also at society (students, families, teachers, citizens) with the final goal of reaching larger audiences and amplifying the project's intended impact. During the RP2, the website has informed, among others, about EDIRE project activities and events, success stories regarding twinning activities (news section), training sessions and seminars (open also to external audiences), research results and public deliverables, and newsletters (publications section). The brochures and flyers can be downloaded from the webpage (publications section).

In summary, EDIRE Project Website includes the following sections:

EDIRE – the main page with the short descriptions of the objectives of the EDIRE project

- **Partners** – This section features the list of EDIRE partners with their corresponding contact details and links to their organizations.
- **Advisory board** – The list features the 10 project Advisory Board Members and institutions they are representing.
- **News** – The entire EDIRE story can be found in this section as it includes all the relevant project activities, events, and initiatives in which the partners have been participating. The contents have been categorized by different category sections such as: Project Activity, Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Activity and Project Meeting.
- **Publications** – This section offers access to EDIRE public deliverables, promotional materials and newsletters.
- **Blog** – The weblog is dedicated to EDIRE partners and all others who want to contribute by dissemination activity through opinion overviews.
- **Trainings** – A section for all EDIRE trainings provided by EDIRE partners, this space contains core information on the training sessions, workshops and open session as well the corresponding registration forms.

- **Project Docs** – This is a special section for limited access (project documents relevant to RP 1 and 2).

Image 1: EDIRE Website Landing Page Screenshot

Table 2: KPI Website Table (according to DCEP in D6.1)

Target values	Indicator: Number of hits	Website link	Means of verification: Reports from the website facility for counting number of accesses.	YEAR
Target Values: >2000 by the end of Y1	3028	www.edire.eu	LINK (TABLE 1)	1
Target Values >3600 by the end of project life	5631	www.edire.eu	LINK (TABLE 2)	2
	2708	www.edire.eu	LINK (TABLE 3)	3
	11367			TOTAL

Image 2: EDIRE Website Footer

3.2 Promotional materials

EDIRE promotional materials were already designed during RP1, with reedition of the printed materials in all project languages. The flyers and brochures had a relevant role in EDIRE communication, enhancing the project's visual identity, visibility, and providing basic information. They were distributed mainly during the summer schools, training sessions, and other events. Both types of documents have been translated into all project languages and can be downloaded at the project Website under the following subpages:

EDiRE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe program for widening participation and spreading excellence under Grant Agreement number 101060145

Project flyer

Project Brochure

Giving continuity to the project’s dissemination and communication plan, project flyers and brochures have been distributed in all events and project activities and sent by email to be interested stakeholders during RP2. In addition, a rollup to be used in events organized by the consortium was designed and printed in the partner countries. To ensure sustainability, only a limited number of promotional materials has been printed aiming to make the most of the distribution electronically. (See annex 1 for project flyer and roll up designs).

Image 3: Project Brochure example

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe program for widening participation and spreading excellence under Grant Agreement number 101060145

Table 3: KPI Brochures and flyers

Project logo, flyers, brochures and advertisements boards will be designed by M3 and translated also in all consortium languages to ensure dissemination activities not only within events of various nature but also on relevant public spaces.	Project brochures	Indicator: Nº of brochures created and distributed (printed version)	Indicator: Nº of brochures created and distributed (printed version and addresses)	Means of verification: Distribution via events and through partners' channels.	YEAR
Target Values: >1500 by the end of Y1 and >3000 by M38	The first edition	200	1682	Link	1
	Project Fylers (Madrid SS)	250	1987	Link	2
	Project brochures (Madrid SS)	250	1987	Link	
	Project Promo Material (Sarajevo Summer School)	150	750	Link	3
	Project Promo Material Final Dissemination Event	500	500	Link	

3.3 Open access scientific publications

EDIRE's starting point for publications was to reach a significant number of scientific articles (at least 5) in open access international peer-reviewed journals by the end of the project, targeting especially flagship publications in the field. Also, highly ranked editions chosen by the researchers in their research domain or in the domain of EDI, as well as national publications of relevance, were included in the list. Academic publications have not only contributed to EDIRE dissemination purposes, but also to enhancing SSST research profile and international reputation, the gained expertise in the field of EDI, with a spill-over effect for the EU partners that have participated in the publication.

3 scientific articles and book chapters have been published since the project began, most of them during RP2, in open access international peer-reviewed journals adhering to HE Open Access policy. Several publications are currently under peer review or editorial processes, 2 have been already accepted and will be published after the project's ending. Also, EDIRE will edit a Monographic book, accepted and published by Verlag Barbara Budrich GmbH by the end of 2026.

Table 4: KPI scientific publications

Measurement	no	Title of publication	Authors	Link	Date	
Short term 5 international publications arisen from EDIRE Mid-term 10 international publications arisen from EDIRE	1	Gender mainstreaming policies in Italian universities: actors, tools, documents	G. Arena, A. C. Taramasso (UNIGE)	to be published	2023	IPPA Conference Paper
	2	Transforming academia through equality, diversity, and inclusion: the experience of Bosnia and Herzegovina with the EDIRE project	R. Bencivenga, C. Leone, C. M. Reale, J. Hasic Telalovic (UNIGE; SSST)	https://teseo.unitn.it/quaderni-dsrs/issue/view/207/221	2024	in A. Tuselli, C. M. Reale, A. Donà, M. M. Coppola (eds.), Gender R-evolutions, Conference proceedings, 2024
	3	Utilizing Artificial Intelligence for Microbiome Decision-Making: Autism Spectrum Disorder in Children from Bosnia and Herzegovina	Dž. Bašić, J. Hasić Telalović, L. Pašić (SSST)	https://www.mdpi.com/2075-4418/14/22/2536	13.Nov.24	Diagnostics 2024 (the Section Diagnostic Microbiology and Infectious Disease)
	4	Smart cities, digital inequalities, and the challenge of inclusion	O.Kolotouchkina, L.Ripoll-González, W.Belabas (UCM)	Smart Cities, Digital Inequalities, and the Challenge of Inclusion	4.Nov.24	MDPI : Smart Cities Special Issue : Inclusive Smart Cities
	5	Academics' Experiences of Work-Life Balance and Work-Life Conflict in a Familialist State: The case of Bosnia and Herzegovina	Caitriona Delaney and Sara Clavero (TU Dublin)	to be published	submitted	

	6	From EDI policy to practice: experiences in European research	Sara Clavero, PhD, Research Fellow, Jasminka Hasic Telalovic, PhD, Associate Professor, Olga Kolotouchkina, PhD, Assistant Professor, Cinzia Leone, PhD, Researcher	Verlag Barbara Budrich GmbH	To be published	This book explores how inclusivity, particularly gender equality and intersectional perspectives, can be meaningfully embedded in research and innovation policies and practices across Europe. It highlights strategies and action plans to improve governance, institutional culture, and policy implementation in order to enhance the societal impact of excellence in research.
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3.4 Project events

3.4.1 Project management meetings (Group 1)

During RP2, management meetings including an open session have been organized on a regular basis, the first one in May 2024 and the second in March 2025. Internal project issues have been discussed in the first part of the management meetings, whereas each meeting included an open session with invited speakers, panels and debates to serve dissemination purposes. The invitation of guest speakers from relevant international academic and research organizations have enhanced the projects' visibility, contributing to the internationalisation and networking goals, offering new options for collaboration between participating organizations and attracting publics from outside the consortium. To ensure larger assistance, the meeting and open panel discussion were offered online. (See annexes 2 and 3 for open panel announcements).

IV Project meeting and open panel (May 7, 2024)

The open panel session titled "Unlocking academic excellence: EDI principles in Western Balkans Higher Education Institutions" was celebrated at SSST and counted with featured speakers from relevant WB higher education institutions. Professors Vesna Žabkar from the University of Ljubljana, Anđela Pepić, EDIRE AB member from the University of Banjaluka and Jovana Mihajlović Trbovc, from the Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Science and Arts together with EDIRE coordinator Jasminka Hasić Telalović from SSST discussed on the EDI policies history, present and future in the region and answered the questions from the public.

V Project meeting and open panel (March 13, 2025)

Project Meeting Open Event: "PhD – Highly Skilled, Yet Precarious: Navigating Institutional Responsibility and the EDI Experience", organized by the University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne, was celebrated on March 13, 2025. Young researchers Virginie Liot (University of Lumière Lyon) and Vanessa Simian (University of Lyon) started the session addressing the adaptation need of doctoral students with disabilities, followed by Joxe Ludovic's (University of Paris Cité-IRD) speech "Dependence, Vulnerability and Harassment in Universities". Following the discussion, Stéphanie Cailles, the vice president for gender equality and anti-discrimination at the University of Reims underlined the importance of reporting measures for harassment, sexism, discrimination and violence at universities. A roundtable discussion by Reims university staff closed the session. Please see annexes for the open event announcement.

Table 5: KPI Project management meetings

Group 1(G1) PROJECT MANAGEMENT MEETINGS	Kick-off meeting	Indicator: N° of external stakeholders involved	Indicator: N° of typologies of entities involved	Indicator Description	Means of verification: attendance proof, presented material, photos, events' reports	Year
Target Values: at least 2 external experts involved in each meeting, in representation of at least 2 different typologies of entities	Sep.22 2022	13	3	1. Prof. Dr. Aleksandra Nikolić, the Minister of Science, Higher Education and Youth of Sarajevo Canton; 2. Prof. Dr. Jasmina Husanović from the University of Tuzla; 3. Academician Prof. Dr. Mirsada Hukić from the Academy of Sciences and Art of Bosnia-Herzegovina	KoM Video KoM	1
	Regular project management meetings	Indicator: N° of external stakeholders involved	Indicator: N° of typologies of entities involved	Indicator Description	Means of verification: attendance proof, presented material, photos, events' reports	Year
	The Second project meeting and panel discussion: Research, university, gender, and EDI principles, February 2023 (online)	3	2	1. Prof. Lyuba Spasova from the Bulgarian Academy of Science; 2. Prof. Sarina Bakić from the University of Sarajevo; 3. Prof. Paolo Piccardo from the University of Genova; 4. Prof. Davide Peddis from the University of Genova	II PM Video II PM	1
	The third meeting: Integrating EDI Principles and Practices in Higher Education and Beyond, Dublin, October 2023	4	2	1. Catherine Bolger (TUD - Gender-Based Violence) 2. Philip Owende (TUD - Race Equality) 3. Catherine Deegan (TUD - Universal Design for Learning) 4. Jeanne McDonagh (Open Doors Initiative, Ireland)	III PM	2

	<p>The fourth meeting: Unlocking academic excellence - EDI principles in Western Balkans Higher Education Institutions (May 2024)</p>	3	2	<p>1. Prof. Vesna Žabkar, University of Ljubljana; 2. Anđela Pepić, University of Banjaluka, EDIRE Advisory Board Member 3. Jovana Mihajlović Trbovc, Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Science and Arts</p>	<p>IV PM</p>	
	<p>“PhD – Highly Skilled, Yet Precarious: Navigating Institutional Responsibility and the EDI Experience.” (March 2025)</p>	5	2	<p>1. Virginie Liot, PhD Candidate in Educational and Training Sciences (University of Lumière Lyon 2) 2. Vanessa Simian, PhD Candidate Contractual Lecturer in Sociology (University of Lyon 1) 3. Ludovic Joxe, Researcher Associate at the at the center for population & Development (University Paris Cité – IRD) 4. Stéphanie Caillies, Vice-President for Gender Equality and Anti-Discrimination, Professor of Cognitive Psychology, University of Reims 5. Béatrice Marin, Vice-President Delegate for Doctoral Training, University of Reims</p>	<p>V PM</p>	3

3.4.2 Group 2: Project dissemination events

EDIRE has organized three events dedicated to project dissemination, both during the RP2 and co-located with the summer schools. These events brought together representatives from all the relevant project target groups, generated awareness and visibility to EDIRE and contributed to enhancing the reputation and academic excellence of SSST and, of partner organizations.

On the one hand, the mid-term dissemination event was organized at UCM in Madrid during summer 24 (June 28, 2024), to expose project findings. During the session, project coordinator Jasminka Hasić-Telalović from SSST presented the main advances of the project, and the Bosnian ambassador H.E. Vesna Andree-Zaimović emphasised the relevance of public diplomacy and international cooperation in the current political situation. Jorge Gómez Sanz, the Vice-Chancellor for Technology and Sustainability at UCM was responsible for wrapping up the event. An active role was given to SSST staff and post-graduate students participating in the summer school, in order to create fruitful networking opportunities. During EDIRE Summer School Madrid 2024, they had the opportunity to meet with academic management and teaching staff from UCM and network with representatives from collaborating organizations, such as Ilunion (civil society organization for disabled persons), the Sports Council of Spain, the Polytechnic University of Madrid and the Embassy of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

On the other hand, the final dissemination event was organized in a hybrid format at SSST in Sarajevo during autumn 25 (October 9) to showcase project achievements and offer recommendations for advancing equality, diversity, and inclusion in the academy in the Western Balkans region. The event was opened by EU project officer Anca-Adrian Cucu and project coordinator Jasminka Hasić-Telalović, who highlighted the relevance of EDIRE in aligning national research environments with European EDI frameworks. The first session, conducted by Emina Ganić, included examples of good practices from the partner organizations presented by Angela Taramasso (UNIGE), Olga Kolotouchkina (UCM), Semira Galijasevic and Jasna Hivziefendic (both from SSST). The second session, focused on EDI in Western Balkans, provided interesting comparative perspectives and shared regional priorities bringing together experts Nikoleta Đukanović from Montenegro, Aleksandra Drečun from Serbia and Sara Clavero from Ireland, at a round table coordinated Hasic Hasić-Telalović. The final event involved stakeholders' representatives from academic and research organizations, project partners, as well as project beneficiaries, especially from SSST staff and students' collective, offering an excellent occasion to present and validate all key project outcomes and to network. The event concluded with a summary of EDIRE's key impacts and results. Testimonials showed how much the project has contributed to the institutional transformation to enhance EDI policies at SSST, to foster academic excellence, and to embed European values within the national research and innovation environment beyond SSST.

Table 6. KPI Dissemination events

GROUP 2 (G2): gathering representatives of all the key EDIRE target groups, will be organised	Project dissemination events	Indicator: Nº of participants	Indicator: Nº of countries represented	Indicator Description	Means of verification: attendance proof, presented material, photos, events' reports	Year
Target Values: >50 external participants per event Target Values: >10 participants per event	Conference: Gender Equality Plans and universities of the future	30	3	1. Prof. Lyuba Spasova from the Bulgarian Academy of Science	Link 1	1
	Mid-term dissemination event To be organized in M18 in Spain by UCM to present main project findings, where an active role will be given to SSST staff to create fruitful networking opportunities (it will be co-located with the first summer school)	50	4	Agenda, pictures and Summer School Schedule	Link 2	2
	Final dissemination event To be organized in M35 in BA by SSST to present final project findings (it will be co- located with the second summer school) and with the Mediterranean Forum. The final event will thus involve a wide variety of stakeholders' representatives (i.e. academic and research sector, policy makers, civil society organisations, non- governmental organisations, etc.) and it will be an excellent occasion to present and validate all key project outcomes.	60	4	Agenda, pictures and Summer School Schedule	Link 3	3

3.4.3 Group 3: Events external to the consortium activities

During RP2, EDIRE consortium members participated in several external events, of relevance with respect to the issues tackled by EDIRE and targeting both scientific and non-scientific communities. External events participation strongly contributed to the need of international collaboration of SSST as well as enhancing the visibility and research profile of the university. In the previous RP1, EDIRE members had already participated in 9 external events by January 2024, nearly reaching the overall KPI of the entire project consisting of 10 external events. During RP2, EDIRE took part in another 9 events. By the end of the project, consortium members have participated in many external events. Especially relevant were the events participated by the project coordinator SSST, linked with WP4 Boosting scientific excellence at SSST objectives.

Table 7: KPI external events

GROUP 3 (G3). Events external to the consortium activities	Title and date of event	Indicator: N° of events attended where EDIRE was presented and promoted	Means of verification: attendance proof, presented material, photos, events' reports	Year/ Month
Target Values : >10 attended external events during the project	Award Ceremony of Western Balkans Women Entrepreneurs (March 2024)	1	https://www.instagram.com/p/C4dj3hxt2Tj/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRlODBiNWFiZA==	2024/3
	7th International Conference on Gender Research in Barcelona (April 2024)	2	https://www.instagram.com/p/C6OzTniNzqy/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFiZA==	2024/4
	Horizon Europe, Horizon Info Days (June, 2024)	3	https://www.instagram.com/p/C76TfNmN_vY/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFiZA==	2024/6

Virtual Mobility event at the Olympic mountain of Bjelašnica, Bosnia and Herzegovina (September 2024)	4	https://edire.eu/edire-project-hosts-successful-virtual-mobility-event/	2024/9
Forum Biosafety: A constant Challenge (October 2024)	5	https://edire.eu/edire-project-at-biosafety-forum-promoting-inclusion-and-innovation/	2024/10
Panel discussion "Future of Creativity: Exploring AI" (December 2024)	6	https://edire.eu/exploring-ais-role-in-education-research-and-creativity/	2024/12
16 Days of Activism Campaign: Influencing Change, promoting equality (December 2024)	7	https://edire.eu/influencing-change-promoting-equality-a-powerful-discussion-at-university-ssst/	2024/12
8th International Conference on Gender Research in Porto (April 2025)	8	https://edire.eu/edire-at-8th-icgr/	2025/04
Twenty-fifth International Conference on Diversity in Organizations, Communities & Nations (June 2025)	9	https://cgscholar.com/cg_event/events/D25es/discussions?custom_schedule_element_id=16782&tab=presentation	2025/06

3.4.4 Group 4: Summer schools and training activities

Summer schools and training sessions were organized in the frameworks of WP4 and WP5, specifically intended for capacity building activities for developing scientific competences for fund-raising, project design and project management. Training sessions responded to the need for spreading and implementing EDI principles and contents in the academia, strengthening organizational structures and research culture and fostering gender equality.

The summer schools responded to the need of enhancing SSST's and partner organizations' internationalisation and networking activities (SO2), highlighting equality, diversity and inclusion as

central axes in research, contributing to the introduction of new lines of study and creating connections between researchers from different areas of knowledge and geographical locations.

As mentioned before, EDIRE has organized 2 summer schools during RP2, the first one in Madrid (June 25-28, 2024) and the second in Sarajevo (June 17-20, 2025).

Madrid summer school summer 2024

Image 4: Madrid summer school participants with the Paralympic swimmer María Delgado (second from the left).

Madrid summer school, celebrated from June 25th to 28th at the Faculty of Communication Science, Complutense University of Madrid, brought together post graduate students, lecturers and experts from Spain, Italy, France, Ireland, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Bulgaria. Several places in Madrid became laboratories for theoretical research and practical application of the principles of equality, diversity and inclusion in diverse areas of scientific knowledge. As a starting point, the Faculty of Communication Sciences of the UCM welcomed the newcomers in a day dedicated to research and creativity, including lectures on EDI principles in research by Sara Clavero and Caitriona Delaney (TUD) and creative thinking by German Rodríguez. Young scholars Shaban Darakchiev (Bulgarian Academy of Science, BAS) and Carlos Vara (UCM) shared tips from their personal experience for academic research.

For its part, the Faculty of Physical Activity and Sport Sciences of the Polytechnic University of Madrid hosted the first workshop on Wednesday 26th, aimed at understanding values in the world of sport, by Javier Tejero. The group of students had the opportunity to practice inclusive sport and meet the Paralympic medallist swimmer María Delgado Nadal, who shared her vision and career in a motivational talk. The second workshop of the day, by Angela Taramasso (UNIGE), dealt with different methods for accessible documents and articles. The project leader from a sister project Milieu, Lyuba Spasova (BAS) and Carla Reale from UNIGE.

On Thursday 27th, it was the turn of Ilunion-Fundación ONCE (the Spanish National Organization for the Blind). Led by Esther Marín, expert in Customer Experience, and Ignacio Velo, Director of Ethics, Sustainability and Alliances at Ilunion, teachers and students visited the facilities and learned more about the employment and training opportunities that the institution offers to people with disabilities. In the afternoon, summer school participants joined La Ronda conference on Artificial Intelligence and its relevance in research, in which EDIRE team members Juan Pavón, Zahia Guessoum and Jasminka Hasić-Telalović shared their vision.

The event was ended by the ambassador of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Vesna Andree-Zaimović, accompanied by the Vice-Rector for Technology and Sustainability, Jorge Gómez Sanz, and EDIRE coordinator Jasminka Hasić-Telalović together with the summer school director Olga Kolotouchkina (UCM).

Thus, the experience has been a learning opportunity through coexistence and knowledge sharing and, at the same time, the emergence of alliances and synergies between different academic institutions and their students.

Madrid summer school was intensively disseminated by the project website and social media, partners mailing lists and information releases, below some examples of social media:

<https://eventos.ucm.es/119147/detail.html>

<https://x.com/UCMccinf/status/1804112300267147320>

<https://x.com/ILUNION/status/1807777577135743051>

The participants overall satisfaction with the summer school was excellent and in particular, 76 % of the students expressed they had learned very much and 24 % quite much about EDI principles.

Graphic 2: Summer school participants survey, question about EDI principles learning outcomes

2. Have you acquired new knowledge about EDI principles in practice or transversal EDI competences?

21 respuestas

Sarajevo summer school summer 2025

Image 5: Sarajevo Summer School participants in front of SSST building.

Sarajevo summer school, welcoming doctoral students and young researchers from the partner organizations in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Italy, Ireland, France, and Spain was held from June 17th to 20th, 2025 at SSST facilities. With its cultural and social diversity and rich heritage, Sarajevo offered an excellent setting for EDI related learning experience. The first day of the school summer school, Tuesday 17th, kicked off with the welcome speeches by the Executive Director of SSST, Emir Ganić, and EDIRE coordinator Jasminka Hasić Telalović, followed by an inspiring lecture on EDI principles in academic research imparted by Sara Clavero and completed by an update about the leadership for EDI in universities offered by Rebecca Grogan from TU Dublin. During the afternoon, students were introduced to the practicalities of making their research more inclusive by the hand of Angela Taramasso.

On Wednesday 18th, the participants had the opportunity to learn from the expertise and research experience of Sabina Ćehajić on post conflict trauma and rebuilding post-conflict societies towards reconciliation. The rest of the day was dedicated to experiential learning; Jasminka Boho gave an immersive session on sign language and Liisa Hänninen set the rules for the hackathon and students were off to discover how inclusive is the city of Sarajevo.

Day 3, Thursday 19th started off with a world café where researchers Lejla Pašić and Semira Galijašević opened and gave tips and tricks to PhD students. The case of AI in relation to RRI was discussed in a panel of experts formed by Jasminka Hasić Telalović, Zahia Guessoum, and Juan Pavon, leaving the

floor open to questions and followed by a reflexive session on the relevance of language as a tool for inclusivity by Emina Bosnjak. The afternoon held an immersive experience to the history of Sarajevo and Islam, with a visit to Gazi Husrev-Bey Library and the Mosque, coordinated and narrated by Dzeveda Garić.

Day 4, Friday 20th opened the discussion to how to empower marginalized groups in politics, by Sabina Cudić, followed by a lecture by Olga Kolotouchkina on paralympic sports and how they impact on the social inclusion of people with disabilities. Participants had the chance to hear firsthand experiences of paralympic champions Selma Purić and Luis Leardy. After the presentation of students' hackaton results and reception of diplomas, Jasminka Hasić Telalović and Olga Kolotouchkina wrapped up the main learnings, and finally, Italian and Spanish Embassy representatives made closure of the summer school.

Sarajevo summer school advances and events were extensively posted by EDIRE's owned social media channels, especially LinkedIn. It is worth mentioning that summer school participants not only reacted and reposted these messages, but also created content based on their own experience. As an example, some of the posts are featured in the following:

<https://www.facebook.com/100086046366587/posts/-edire-summer-school-2025-sarajevoabout-the-schooledire-summer-school-will-gathe/625680540310153/>

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/edire_edire-edi-principles-activity-7310372245925773314-6TrT/

Training activities

During RP1, by the end of February 2024, 16 training activities had already been organized and the end-of-project target value (a minimum of 12 training activities during the project) was reached. 14 training sessions correspond to the RP2 and are featured in the above table. All these training activities carried out during RP2 exceeded the expected results but were considered relevant and contributed to enhancing the participants' competences in EDIRE's core subjects.

A more detailed account on training activities and summer schools can be found in WP4 and WP5 deliverables (see D4.2, D4.3, D5.2 and D5.3.).

Table 8: KPI for Group 4: Summer Schools/trainings/seminars for capacity building in WP4

GROUP 4 (G4): Summer schools/trainings/	Name and date of the event	Indicator: N° of events	Type of the event	Means of verification: Attendance proof, presented material, photos, events' reports.	Year/ Month
	"SSST Capacity Building EDIRE trainings I Day" (Cinzia Leone & Liisa Hänninen) (March 6, 2024)	1	Capacity Building	Link 18	M19
	"SSST Capacity Building EDIRE trainings II Day" (Olga Kolotuchkina) (March 7, 2024)	2	Capacity Building	Link 19	M19
	"Leadership for Equality, Diversity and Inclusion in Universities and Research Organisations" (Yvonne Galligan) (March 27, 2024)	3	Training	Link 20	M19
	"Social Signals in Affective Cognitive Sciences: Recognition and Production" (Ali Oker) (June 4, 2024)	4	Training	Link 21	M21
	Seminar on data collection and gender balance (Angela Celeste Taramasso & Francesca Bagnoli) (July 10, 2024)	5	Capacity Building	Link 22	M22
	Summer School in Madrid (José Antonio Ruiz San Román, Elisa Brey, Jasminka Hasić-Telalović, Olga Kolotouchkina, Liisa Hanninen, Sara Clavero, Caitriona Delaney, Angela Taramasso, Carla Reale, Shaban Darakchiev & Carlos Vara) (July 25-28, 2024)	6	Summer School	Link 23	M22
	Virtual mobility "Good practices in Open Science" (Lindsay Dawling, Paul Hynds, Lidija Živković, Mary Lou O'Neill, Jasminka Hasić – Telalović, Mirsada Hukić) (September, 12-13, 2024)	7	Virtual mobility (training)	Link 24b	M24

	Spreading Excellence in Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion in the Western Balkans (Jasminka Hasić Telalović) (December 11, 2024)	8	Training	Link 24	M27
	RRI, gender and intersectionality (Carla Maria Reale) (December 21, 2024)	9	Training	Link 25	M27
	Jean Monnet Info Session for Research Growth at SSST (Maja Savić-Bojanić & Semira Galijašević) (January 10, 2025)	10	Info session	Link 26	M28
	The Missing Link in EDI and The What, Why and How of Using Narratives in Intersectional Research (Sofiane Mahi & Caitriona Delaney) (March 14th, 2025)	11	Training	Link 27	M30
	Fundamental concepts of HPC, IA and quantum computing (Arnaud Renard, Théo Barrios and Frédéric Maguire) (April 10, 2025)	12	Training	Link 28	M31
	AI for managers (Théo Barrios) (April 22, 2025)	13	Training	Link 29	M31
	EDIRE management training: the manager as a creator of team dynamics and inclusion (Yellow Brick & Marija) (September 16-17, 2025)	14	Training	Link 30	M37
Total RP 2 KPIS	14 training sessions				

3.5 Project newsletter

EDIRE newsletter has been one of the core dissemination and communication tools for the project, contributing to the SSST visibility, international profile, and research reputation as well as spreading EDI-related culture and content. It has been produced by SSST and other partners roughly every 6 months and distributed to other relevant research institutions and universities in BA. It has been translated to BSC. Also, consortium members have disseminated the newsletters via their institutional channels and professional networks. In addition, external stakeholders have also been involved in the newsletter's distribution, especially using Social Media sharing. Among others, EDIRE newsletters contain past, ongoing and future project activities and include short interviews to stakeholders and partners' members, as well as project outcomes.

Altogether, 6 Newsletters have been published and publicized on EDIRE Website subpage, where issues 4-5 correspond to the RP 2 (see annex 4 for newsletter covers):

[Newsletter I](#) (autumn 2022 and winter 2022/23)

[Newsletter II](#) (spring and summer 2023)

[Newsletter III](#) (autumn 2023 and winter 2023/24)

[Newsletter IV](#) (spring and summer 2024)

[Newsletter V](#) (autumn 2024 and winter 2024/2025)

[Newsletter VI](#) (spring and summer 2025)

Image 4: The content of EDIRE Newsletter 4 – example

Table 9: KPI Project Newsletters

Project Newsletter	Indicator: N° of issues and N° of addressees	Means of verification: E-Newsletter on the website and number of downloads and e-mails sent	Year
Target values: 1 issue every 6 months At least 500 addressees by issue and 10% yearly increase			
The first Newsletter	Issue 1: 967	LINK 1	Y1
The second Newsletter	Issue 2: 876	LINK 2	
The third Newsletter	Issue 3: 1247	LINK 3	
The fourth Newsletter	Issue 4: 1243	LINK 4	Y2
The fifth Newsletter	Issue 5: 1310	LINK 5	Y3
The sixth Newsletter	Issue 6: 1400	LINK 6	Y3

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe program for widening participation and spreading excellence under Grant Agreement number 101060145

3.6. Liaison activities

The consortium has dedicated intensive efforts to liaise with international, EU, national, international projects on the same, or similar, issues, thus exchanging good practices and ideas, contributing to mainstreaming and then constantly updating the developed results. Particular attention has been devoted to initiatives funded in the WB, making leverages by connecting EDIRE with partners' other previous/current initiatives and exploring new contacts. In this sense, especially international conferences have proved to provide an outstanding opportunity for liaison with similar initiatives. The KPI of reaching out to at least 3 other relevant projects was reached already during the RP1. EDIRE partners have established collaborations, e.g. shared training sessions, meetings and invitations to project events with several EU funded projects, including Budget-It, MILIEU, Gender-Ex, Step, Ulysses, Xformal, Affectance, Inspire and Embedding RRI in WB Countries initiative.

Table 10: KPI Liaison activities

Activities	Name of the event/context of the liaison activity	Project name and ID	Indicator: N° of EU funded project addressed	Means of verification: Contents of dissemination and communication packages (D6.3 and D6.4)	Year
<u>Target Values:</u> At least 3 projects during the project	Presentation at Responsible Research and Innovation concepts in STEM education conference	Embedding RRI in Western Balkan Countries: Enhancement of Self-Sustaining R&I Ecosystems grant agreement (GA) No. 101006279	1	Link 1 Link 2 Link 3 Link 4	1
	Collaboration with Budget-It project	Budget-It GA N° 1010904391	1	Link 5	1
	Iceland Conference of the Europeanists: Fostering Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion in Academia: Lessons Learned and Good Practices	Gender-Ex Project (GA N° 952798), MILIEU Project (GA N° 952369), ULYSSEUS GA N° 101035809) and XFORMAL (GA N° 101008184)	4	Link 6	1
	Collaboration with Affectance and project supervision	Affectance project (MSCA-Una4Career, GA N° 847635)	1	Link 7	1-3

	Collaboration with INSPIRE project; Next Steps CoP (Community of Practice)	INSPIRE GA N° 101058537	1	Link 8 Link 9	3
	Best practices in adding an EDI dimension to research and teaching	ULYSSEUS GA N° 101035809) STEP GA N° 101078933	2	Link 10	3

3.7 Social media

EDIRE social media platforms together with the website have been used as the main communication channel for project activities to be disseminated and communicated, with the aim of interacting with target audiences and the public in all consortium countries. Social media serves as an outstanding channel for spreading news and promoting EDIRE activities, contributing to SSST research profile, international and national visibility and attractiveness as an academic institution. The social media channels used by EDIRE have been Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, and YouTube.

Following EDIRE Social Media Strategy, the focus has been on ongoing activities, publications and events, both those organized by the project and those attended by the consortium members. Specific project hashtags have been selected and used for quantitative assessment. Also, a Blog (access through EDIRE website) was established, where the end-of-project KPI of 5 publications was reached.

	Social media	Indicator: N° of Likes and Shares, Tweets and Retweets with certain selected hashtags		Means of verification: reports from such networks to be kept alive via regular posting and monitoring; blog statistics		Y2	
		Likes	Shares	Followers			
	Facebook	606	25	143	LINK FB		
	Instagram	250	10	150	LINK IG		
	LinkedIN	200	120	250	LINK LNKD		
	Youtube	9	200	4	@edireedire		
	BLOG	Indicator: N° of publications on the web blog		Means of verification: reports from such networks to be kept alive via regular posting and monitoring; blog statistics		Y3	
	Lessons from the EDIRE Summer School: A Journey of Learning, Connection, and Inspiration	1		Blog 4			
	“Casting a Wider Net: Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion in the Fishing Sector”	1		Blog 5			
	Social Media	Indicator: N° of Likes and Shares, Tweets and Retweets with certain selected hashtags		Means of verification: reports from such networks to be kept alive via regular posting and monitoring; blog statistics			
Facebook	700	30	145	LINK FB			
Instagram	1149	30	179	LINK IG			
LinkedIN	38,593	250	383	LINK LNKD			
Youtube	12	414	21	@edireedire			

3.8 Press releases and media relations

Project results and relevant EDIRE moments have been communicated and disseminated through media (general press, magazines for audiences interested in EDI initiatives - women, LGBTQ+, people with disabilities- radio, television) via press releases, press briefings and interviews. Maximum geographical coverage beyond the countries represented in the consortium was one of the project communication objectives, with a special focus on WB and other widening countries characterised by similar situations. The media coverage has contributed to the projects' visibility and reputational goals, enhancing SSST attractiveness and research profile among academic and non-academic publics especially in Bosnia Herzegovina.

By the end of year 1, already 12 media mentions had been achieved, half of them on radio or TV; during years 2 and 3 SSST gained 4 earned media appearances, totalling 17 media KPIs by the end of the project, reaching the target value for media.

Table 12: KPI of Press Release and Media

DC in general press, magazines for audiences interested in EDI initiatives - women, LGBTQ+, people with disabilities- radio, television) via press releases and press briefings.	Press releases and media relations (M1-M36)	Indicator: N° of quotes on newspapers, television, websites; Radio and TV contributions	Means of verification: Proof of publications or videos	Year
Target Values: At least 15 articles in either newspaper/magazines/radio by the end of the project Target Values: at least 2 reports per year on radio/TV	The announcement that SSST will be coordinating the Horizon Europe project that is starting in September (<i>Klix.ba</i>)	portal	https://www.klix.ba/biznis/sarajevo-school-of-science-and-technology-jedini-u-bih-sa-odobrenim-horizon-europe-projektom/220527128;	1

programmes by M38	Information about the project start and announcement of the Kick of Meeting (<i>Klix.ba</i>)	portal	https://www.klix.ba/biznis/inauguracija-horizon-europe-edire-projekta/220919108?fbclid=IwAR1C2it65G0vwfWXRfXL89uheS0vvK7j4VsGk0mbzVDHDNYW-JeTkPLakaM
	Announcement for: Interview on research and science and promotion of EDIRE project by Jasminka Hasić Telalović (<i>N1Info BA</i>)	Portal	https://n1info.ba/vijesti/bh-naucnica-za-n1-ne-trebamo-se-plasiti-robot-a-ali-neki-poslovi-ce-nestati/
		TV	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=awFeg9AkUV4
		portal	https://n1info.ba/vijesti/jasminka-hasic-telalovic-gosca-izvan-okvira-veceras-od-20-sati/
	General information on EDIRE	website	https://wbc-rti.info/object/project/23468
	The conference on gender "R-Evolutions". Presentation of paper "Transforming Academia through Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion: The experience of Bosnia Herzegovina with the EDiRe project"	TV	TV Italy
website		https://webmagazine.unitn.it/evento/sociologia/111961/gender-r-evolutions-immaginare-l-inevitabile-sovertire-l-impossibile	

	Interview on research and science and promotion of EDIRE project by Jasminka Hasić Telalović	TV	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UDtJt2GS7WQ	
	Interview on International Women's Day (<i>RadioM</i>)	Radio	https://radiom.ba/radio/prof-dr-jasminka-hasic-telalovic-o-zenama-u-nauci/	
			https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DS9RUGV7eRM	
	ChooseSTEMFuture RCC Campaigning	website	https://www.rcc.int/news/794/bregu-to-have-wider-choices-earn-more-and-live-better--choose-stem-future	
	BH Horizon Europe Info Day - EDIRE as a success story	TV	https://www.dropbox.com/s/bbamlf8r32g6knl/Screen%20Recording%202024-06-13%20at%2010.07.46%20AM.mov?dl=0	2
	EDIRE Summer School in Madrid	portal	https://www.klix.ba/biznis/unapredjenje-obrazovanja-kroz-edire-univerzitet-ssst-na-putu-ka-jednakosti-u-akademskoj-zajednici/240703122	
		portal	https://radiosarajevo.ba/metromahala teme/odrzana-lijetna-skola-edire-u-spaniji-prisustvovala-i-ambasadorica-bih-vesna-andree-zaimovic/551894	

		TV	https://face.ba/izdvojeno/unapredjenje-obrazovanja-kroz-projekat-edire-univerzitet-ssst-potvrduje-liderstvo-na-putu-ka-jednakosti-u-akademskoj-zajednici/419806/	
	International Day of Women and Girls in Science	Magazine	https://www.urbanmagazin.ba/sci-she-one-stvaraju-svijet-kroz-nauku-inspirisao-mlade-generacije-u-bosni-i-hercegovini/ https://www.urbanmagazin.ba/sci-she-one-stvaraju-svijet-kroz-nauku-inspirisao-mlade-generacije-u-bosni-i-hercegovini/	3
		TV	https://federalna.ba/sci-she-one-stvaraju-svijet-kroz-nauku-gpccz	
		TV	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7O8etzNDvF4	
HORIZON EUROPE Projects			https://youtu.be/KVuVptt886g	
EDIRE Final Dissemination Event		portal	https://www.klix.ba/biznis/zavrzni-dogadaj-projekta-edire-obiljezio-novu-eru-jednakosti-i-inkluzije-u-nauci/251024042	
	Ljepota i zdravlje	Magazine	To be published	

3.9 Participation in Open-Science events

EDIRE communication plan also included plans for participation in Open-Science events, apart from the Open Sessions included in the project's regular management meetings, celebrated on a 6-month basis (see chapter 3.4.1). These other options for Open-Science participation included science festivals, open sessions, panels and debates, school fairs, events with students' organizations and HUBs, and existing annual events. Open-Science events have been relevant for enhancing SSST visibility, networking and internationalisation purposes, as well as sharing knowledge on EDI-related contents. Altogether, EDIRE participated in 4 Open-Science events, exceeding the expected KPI of 3 events during the project.

The above table features the main events from both RP1 and RP2.

Table 13: KPI Open-Science events during RP1 and RP2

Activity	Participation in Open-Science events (M6-M36)	Means of verification: attendance proof, presented materials, photos, reports	YEAR & RP
Target value: >3 events attended during the project	16 days of activism: 3 weeks of conferences, lectures and workshops where EDIRE was presented. The participants had the opportunity to listen about equality, diversity, and inclusion connected to the prevention of sexual harassment and gender-based discrimination at the universities (November 2022)	https://edire.eu/16-days-of-activism-against-gender-based-violence-campaign-at-ssst/	1 (RP1)
	14 Days of Bhaaas (The University of Tuzla): Know-how session and panel discussion: Overcoming Obstacles and Seizing Opportunities in Europe's Research and Innovation Landscape. The project coordinator, Jasminka Hasić Telalović, presented EDIRE by explaining the importance of Horizon programs for projects (June 2023)	https://edire.eu/navigating-the-horizon-overcoming-obstacles-and-seizing-opportunities-in-europes-research-and-innovation-landscape/	1 (RP1)
	Digital Science: 2 days of conferences on open science in a changing global system. Jasminka Hasić Telalović participated as a panelist, highlighting the need for a policy strategy and structural support to achieve more inclusive and equitable research (September 2024)	https://edire.eu/exploring-open-science-insights-from-the-earma-conference/	3 (RP2)

	<p>SCI-SHE: They create the world through science: To commemorate the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, an open science event was held for people of different age groups. Jasminka Hasić Telalović shared the importance of equality, diversity, and inclusion for women in STEM fields (February, 2025)</p>	<p>https://edire.eu/sci-she-international-day-of-women-and-girls-in-science/</p>	<p>3 (RP2)</p>
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3.10 Other dissemination and communication activities (not included in the GA)

EDIRE partners performed additional dissemination and communication activities that were not included in the GA requirements but have contributed to the project's communicational outreach, project visibility, and to awareness raising in EDI-related policies and practices. Many of these are minor events organized at the participating universities, such as lectures and student workshops on EDI, GE and similar. An example of these activities is the yearly celebration of RRI and EDI workshops within the master's degree in social communication at UCM.

4. The future of EDIRE dissemination and communication activities

As seen in the previous chapters, the current deliverable covers all the relevant dissemination and communication efforts during RP2, it also evaluates the achievement of the CD goals established in the initial plan (D6.1). Dissemination and communication activities have strongly contributed to reaching the project's expected impacts and will continue doing so because EDIRE has established both short term (by the end of the project) and medium-term objectives/target values (e.g. 2 years after the project has finished). The aim has been to maximize the exploitation of outcomes and lessons learned by taking all emerging opportunities to communicate and mainstream the results and foster their transferability. EDIRE has elaborated detailed plans to ensure the sustainability and exploitation of the main EDIRE twinning mechanisms, contained in a parallel deliverable D6.4.

After the project has ended, EDIRE will undertake the following mid-term measures (2-5 years after end-date) to give continuity to EDIRE dissemination and communication plans and respond to the benchmark KPIs, as foreseen in the GA:

- Keeping alive and updating the Website for 5 years after the project's end.
- Obtaining 5 new international publications, summing a total of 10 in mid-term.
- Organizing, delivering and communicating about 2 new summer schools.
- Organizing, delivering and communicating 6 new online training courses on project design and management.
- Providing training materials in open access. A selection of the training courses is available at EDIRE's Youtube channel (please see <https://www.youtube.com/@edireedire>).

As mentioned in previous reports, EDIRE was the first Horizon Europe coordinated by an institution in Bosnia and Herzegovina and thus, an opportunity to strengthen the country's participation in EU funding programs. Building on the relation with other research performing institutions in Bosnia and Herzegovina and outside the count, the creation of new project proposals and collaborations will be fostered also after the project ends. These new initiatives will strengthen the EDI research capabilities and outcomes in the country and in the WB region. The post EDIRE action plan includes the following activities:

- Joined organization and participation in new projects, seminars and conferences
- Meetings of doctoral programmes and engagement of doctoral students;

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In addition, SSST and partners will continue participating in external events, such as conferences, workshops and open-access events, both internationally and in each participating country, to contribute to the exploitation of project results, methods and plans. Each university will use their existing resources to give continuity to EDIRE DC sustainability plans.

UCM has several internal media channels for project exploitation, including a radio station, a newspaper, news on faculty websites, and social media (X, LinkedIn, Facebook), which will be continuously used to share results among the university's academic community. EDIRE results continue being disseminated through institutional websites of the academic community, such as the ITC (Institute for the Technology of Knowledge). In addition, project results will be made available through conferences, research meetings and student workshops at the university (e.g. master's degree in social communication). After the end of the project, EDIRE final outcomes will be shared with the academic community, Interdisciplinary research groups, the School of Doctoral and Postgraduate Programmes, as well as with the Unit of Scientific Communication, in charge of distributing a national press release about the project findings. The Summer School hosted by UCM in July 2024 enabled the postgraduate students to do international contacts, permitting them to explore international research and networking opportunities for the near future.

At TUD, project partners will be invited to contribute to RINCE and EDI activities to disseminate results beyond the project's lifetime. These include academic visits, seminars, training, blogs, and newsletters, as well as other projects' events led by RINCE (conferences, workshops, etc.) An exchange programme between SSST and TU Dublin R&I offices has been set up as a mutual learning and knowledge exchange mechanism, with the goal of integrating EDIRE's results in the research policy of both institutions.

The project scope, main milestones and results have been shared by UNIGE with the academic, student and civil communities in different ways and we will continue with this articulated strategy. EDIRE was presented in front of the UNIGE Equal Opportunities Committee and will be mentioned continuously within its activities as well as in gender-research-specific seminars and workshops that will be periodically held to incentive studies and sensibility on this topic. UNIGE has recently implemented a new course proposal focussing on EDI topics, with a special focus on STEM fields. In addition, a cycle of recordings in English is planned for UNIGE Radio. This web radio can be reached via the internet from all over the planet and will be used to share worldwide the project results and short interviews. In this cycle of recording, the project will be presented along with its main results and milestones. The recordings, although coordinated by the EDIRE UNIGE team, will be operated by students, both in the role of 'apprentice journalists' and interviewees, for a better understanding of students' perceptions of the topics raised by the project. Following the GEP action, UNIGE team will disseminate EDIRE result involving the newly established Early-Stage Researchers' Group for Equality and Inclusion.

URCA has a very active communication service that provides several communication solutions: Newsletter, Press Relations, Organization of institutional events, Website, and Several social media (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn...). The URCA team interacts with this service for sharing results among the

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academic community of the URCA, other French universities and other strategic actors. The research groups of the URCA group members will use the websites of their departments and research groups to distribute EDIRE results. Some results of the EDIRE project will be submitted to national and international ITC conferences at ITC and journal. The URCA group will also contact the different departments and master's to share the main topics and results of EDIRE.

5. Conclusions

EDIRE projects' dissemination and communication efforts carried out by the consortium have reached the expected objectives in terms of KPIs, and in most cases, the expectations have been exceeded as shown in the table below. Still, many of the activities are still ongoing and will continue after the project ends, among others the publications, conference attendance and staff trainings. The ORPA office at SSST will keep working in SSST internationalization and giving support to the university's staff in project administration and new proposals.

Nevertheless, there are elements and intangible results that cannot be measured by usual KPIs, such as those related to soft skills, teams individual learnings on EDI and human connections, positive work climate and willingness to keep collaborating that will no doubt contribute to the future of the consortium members shared actions in the future, beyond those established in the GA.

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6. Summary outline of communication and dissemination results by M38

Table 14: Summary outline of CD global results by M38

Activity	To be completed by M38	Results by M38: achieved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> , exceeded <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> or to be completed in short term
Project visual identity	<i>Continually use designs for all communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities.</i>	Achieved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Promotional materials	<i>Distribution of >3000 promotional flyers and brochures.</i> 8.251 pieces distributed.	Exceeded <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Website	<i>All sections regularly filled with the relevant data and indicated measures achieved. >3600 hits by the end of project.</i> 2307 hits by M38 reached.	Exceeded <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Publications, including scientific articles will be published in international peer-reviewed indexed journals, respecting the Open Access policy	The publication plan has been executed. At least 5 submissions. 3 EDIRE papers have been published and 2 have been accepted, currently under editorial process. Also, a book edited by EDIRE has been accepted by Verlag Barbara Budrich, to be published by end of 2026.	Achieved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Newsletter	Two yearly issues: M24, M30, M38	Achieved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Project management meetings with open sessions	<p><i>Regular meetings with open sessions. At least 2 experts from 2 kinds of organizations in the open sessions.</i></p> <p>The IV and V Project meetings included an open session with several experts.</p>	Achieved ✓
Dissemination events	<p><i>Organizing 2 events with >50 external and >10 internal participants.</i></p> <p>Two dissemination events successfully celebrated: -July 2024: Midterm dissemination event in Madrid -October 2025 Final dissemination event in Sarajevo</p> <p>Both events reached at least 10 internal participants and came close to 50 external participants, with more than 5 countries represented.</p>	Achieved ✓
Events external to the consortium activities	<p><i>More than 10 external events attended during the project.</i></p> <p>During RP2, EDIRE attended 9 external events (and during RP1 9 events), summing 18 events during the project.</p>	Exceeded ✓ ✓
Liaison activities	<p><i>At least 3 projects addressed during the project.</i></p> <p>EDIRE addressed 10 projects through 6 different activities during the project.</p>	Exceeded ✓ ✓
<i>Summer-schools/trainings</i>	<p><i>Training completed according to the plan. At least 12 training sessions and 2 summer schools during the project.</i></p> <p>Madrid (M 23) and Sarajevo summer schools were celebrated (M35) and EDIRE organized 14 training sessions</p>	Exceeded ✓ ✓

	during RP2 and 16 during RP1, a total of 30 during the project.	
<i>Social media</i>	<p><i>Meeting the planned success indicators (KPI) for social media and at least 5 publications on the web blog.</i></p> <p>Social media metrics reached and 6 blog publications by the end of the project.</p>	<p>Social media: to be completed and in some cases, results exceeded (Linkedin)</p> <p>Web blog: Exceeded <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<i>Press releases and media coverage</i>	<p><i>Meeting the planned success indicators. At least 17 pieces of media coverage.</i></p> <p>EDIRE has gained 17 media mentions.</p>	Achieved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Open science events</i>	<p><i>Meeting the planned success indicators. At least 3 open events participated.</i></p> <p>EDIRE has participated in 4 events during the project.</p>	Exceeded <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Annexes

Annex 1: EDiRE flyer and rollup designs

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The poster features a yellow background with abstract white and light yellow shapes. At the top left is the European Union flag with the text 'Funded by the European Union'. At the top right is the 'EDiRE' logo. The main title 'EQUALITY, DIVERSITY AND INCLUSION FOR RESEARCH ENHANCEMENT IN B&H' is written in large, bold, blue capital letters. Below the title, the dates 'SEPT 2022 - 2025' are displayed in a smaller blue font. A vertical column of small yellow dots is positioned to the right of the title, and a horizontal row of small yellow dots is below the dates.

UNIVERSITY PARTNERS

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Annex 2: Announcements of EDIRE Open Panel on May 7th 2024

Unlocking academic excellence: EDI principles in Western Balkans Higher Education Institutions

*Open Panel:
May 7th, 2024, 12.00, Zoom*

Unlocking academic excellence: EDI principles in Western Balkans Higher Education Institutions

*Open Panel:
May 7th, 2024, 12.00, Zoom*

VESNA ŽABKAR
UNIVERSITY OF LJUBLJANA

Unlocking academic excellence: EDI principles in Western Balkans Higher Education Institutions

*Open Panel:
May 7th, 2024, 12.00, Zoom*

ANĐELA PEPIĆ
UNIVERSITY OF BANJALUKA

Unlocking academic excellence: EDI principles in Western Balkans Higher Education Institutions

*Open Panel:
May 7th, 2024, 12.00, Zoom*

**JOVANA MIHAJLOVIĆ-
TRBOVC**
RESEARCH CENTRE OF THE
SLOVENIAN ACADEMY OF
SCIENCES AND ARTS

Unlocking academic excellence: EDI principles in Western Balkans Higher Education Institutions

*Open Panel:
May 7th, 2024, 12.00, Zoom*

**JASMINKA HASIĆ
TELALOVIĆ**
SSST EDIRE PROJECT
COORDINATOR AND
OPEN SESSION MODERATOR

Annex 3: Announcement of EDIRE Open Panel on March 13th, 2025

EDIRE Project Meeting Open Event
13.03.2025 9AM - 1PM

PhD – Highly Skilled, Yet Precarious: Navigating Institutional Responsibility and the EDI Experience

08:45 – 09:00 | Welcome

09:00 – 09:15 | Introduction

09:15 – 09:55

Intervention 1: How Can the Adaptation Needs of Doctoral Students with Disabilities Be Addressed within Various Supervisory Structures?

Speakers: Virginie Liot, PhD Candidate in Educational and Training Sciences (ECP / University of Lumière Lyon 2)
Vanessa Simian, PhD Candidate Contractual Lecturer in Sociology (L-VIS / University of Lyon 1)

Duration: 30-minute talk + 10-minute Q&A

09:55 – 10:35

Intervention 2: Dependence, Vulnerability and Harassment in Universities: Doctoral Supervision Through the lens of care

Speaker: Ludovic Joxe, Researcher Associate at the center for population & Development (University Paris Cité – IRD), France

Duration: 30-minute talk + 10-minute Q&A

10:35 – 10:50 | Coffee Break

10:50 – 11:30

Intervention 3: The Importance of Reporting Procedures for Harassment, Sexism, Discrimination, and Violence in Universities: The Case of the University of Reims (URCA)

Speaker: Stéphanie Caillies, Vice-President for Gender Equality and Anti-Discrimination, Professor of Cognitive Psychology, University of Reims

Duration: 30-minute talk + 10-minute Q&A

11:30 – 12:30 | Roundtable Discussion

Participants:

- EDIRE European Partner
- Béatrice Marin, Vice-President Delegate for Doctoral Training, University of Reims
- Sofiane Mahi, PhD Candidate, Research Engineer EDIRE Project
- Stéphanie Caillies, Vice-President for Gender Equality and Anti-Discrimination, Professor of Cognitive Psychology, University of Reims

Key Topics:

- The Paradox of Doctoral Training: High Expertise and Structural Vulnerability
- Fostering an Inclusive Doctoral Path: From Disability Accommodation to EDI Culture
- Rethinking Supervision: Care, Harassment Prevention, and Reporting Mechanisms
- PhD Candidates as the Future of Academia: Cultivating Accountability and Transformative Leadership

13:00 | Closing Remarks and Conclusions

■ The contents of this website are the sole responsibility of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe program for widening participation and spreading excellence under Grant Agreement number 101060145.

Annex 4: Examples of EDIRE newsletter covers

EDiRE Newsletter 4/2024

Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion for research enhancement (EDIRE) in Bosnia and Herzegovina, is a European Union Horizon Europe project, coordinated by the University Sarajevo School of Science and Technology (SSST) which started in September 2022.

Project partners include prominent universities from Europe: TU Dublin (Ireland), The University of Genoa (Italy), The Complutense University of Madrid (Spain), and The University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne (France).

The aim of the Project is to create a collaborative network between the University Sarajevo School of Science and Technology (SSST) and four renowned research institutions in France, Italy, Ireland, and Spain, with the final aim of increasing SSST research profile, boosting its research capacity, especially in the field of Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI).

Within the three years, EDIRE is focused on reinforcing SSST's science and research structure by adopting good practices and knowledge-sharing networks with partner universities from Italy, Spain, France, and Ireland. This project also aims to share knowledge across the BiH university network, and scientific institutions.

SSST Capacity Building EDIRE Trainings

March 6th – 7th, 2024

Capacity building trainings were organised at the University Sarajevo School of Science and Technology on March 6th and 7th. On the first training day, two EDIRE training sessions were organized to enhance the capacities of SSST. Both training sessions aimed to strengthen and enhance the capacities of SSST, targeting representatives of administration and management.

[Learn more...](#)

On the second training day, we continued with the EDIRE activities aimed at strengthening the capacities of SSST staff. The first part of the agenda was dedicated to presenting the work of the Office of Research Projects and Administration (ORPA). The second part of the training day was dedicated for the EDIRE training for SSST academic staff titled: "From Abstract to Published Paper", conducted by Olga Kolotuchkina, a representative of Complutense University of Madrid.

[Learn more...](#)

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Within the next three years, EDiRE will focus on reinforcing SSST's science and research structure by adopting good practices and knowledge-sharing networks with partner universities from Italy, Spain, France, and Ireland. This project also aims to share knowledge across the BiH university network, and scientific institutions.

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